

Role of Vitamin D and Calcium for Prevention of Postmenopausal and Senile Osteoporosis

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Abstract:

Background: Osteoporosis, characterized by decreased bone density and increased fracture risk, is a significant health concern among older adults. This systematic review aims to evaluate the efficacy of vitamin D and calcium supplementation in preventing postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis.

Methods: This systematic review was conducted according to guidelines of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA). A comprehensive literature search was conducted across multiple databases, including PubMed, Science Direct and Cochrane Library to identify randomized controlled trials (RCTs) published from 2014 to 2024. The search terms included "calcium", "vitamin D", "postmenopausal osteoporosis", "senile osteoporosis" and "fracture". Studies were included if they assessed the effects of calcium and/or vitamin D supplementation on postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis in older adults.

Results: Sample sizes in the selected studies ranged from 79 to 7195, indicating both large population studies and smaller focused trials. Participants' ages range from approximately 50 to 86 years old. The interventions varied significantly across studies, involving different dosages of calcium and vitamin D: calcium dosages ranged from 300 mg to 1200 mg per day and Vitamin D dosages varied from 400 IU to 10,000 IU per day, with multiple forms (e.g., cholecalciferol). The studies generally suggest that adequate dosages of calcium and vitamin D, either alone or in combination with other factors like exercise and nutrition, can have significant benefits for bone health, particularly in vulnerable populations like postmenopausal women and the elderly.

Conclusion: This systematic review concludes that calcium and vitamin D supplementation plays a vital role in preventing postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis and reducing fracture risk in older adults. The evidence supports the combined use of these nutrients, particularly in populations at risk for deficiency.

Keywords: Vitamin D, Calcium Supplementation, Postmenopausal Osteoporosis, Senile Osteoporosis.

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Introduction

Osteoporosis is a metabolic bone disorder with high incidence. It is characterized by decreased bone mass, increased bone fragility and deteriorated microstructural bone tissues [1]. It occurs due to the imbalance between bone formation and bone resorption [2]. There are two main categories of osteoporosis: primary and secondary. Primary osteoporosis is the most common type which includes postmenopausal osteoporosis and senile osteoporosis.

Secondary osteoporosis is caused by etiological mechanism. Postmenopausal osteoporosis is caused by loss of estrogen and androgen resulting in increased bone turnover, with bone resorption exceeding bone formation and significant loss of trabecular bone compared with cortical bone.

Senile osteoporosis is caused by systemic senescence and occurs in older age group of people. Senile osteoporosis, characterized by decreased bone density and increased fracture risk, is a significant health concern among older adults. Vitamin D and calcium are critical nutrients for maintaining bone health, and their supplementation has been widely recommended to prevent osteoporosis and associated fractures.

This systematic review aims to evaluate the efficacy of vitamin D and calcium supplementation in preventing postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis, focusing on randomized controlled trials (RCTs). Osteoporosis is a systemic skeletal disease involving bone tissues, leading to bone fragility and susceptibility to fracture [3]. As the

world population ages, the number of patients with osteoporosis and resulting fractures is expected to increase [4]. Vitamin D and calcium play crucial roles in the prevention of postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis, particularly in older adults. Their combined effects on bone health have been extensively studied, revealing significant insights into their physiological functions and therapeutic potential.

Calcium is essential for various bodily functions, notably skeletal mineralization. Over 99% of the body's calcium is stored in bones, contributing to their strength and acting as a reservoir to maintain normal plasma calcium levels. Adequate dietary calcium intake is vital to prevent bone loss, particularly in older adults who may experience increased calcium excretion and decreased absorption due to aging. Studies indicate that a daily intake of at least 1200 mg of calcium can help mitigate postmenopausal bone loss and reduce fracture risk, particularly in women more than five years post-menopause [5, 6].

Vitamin D is crucial for enhancing calcium absorption from the gut and regulating calcium and phosphate metabolism. It stimulates bone matrix formation and maturation, and its deficiency is linked to increased osteoporosis risk. Optimal vitamin D levels are necessary for effective calcium utilization; thus, supplementation is often recommended, especially for older adults who may have limited sun exposure and dietary intake. Research shows that vitamin D supplementation can lead to significant increases in serum 25(OH)D levels, which are associated with improved bone density and reduced fracture incidence [5, 7, 8].

The combination of calcium and vitamin D supplementation has shown more consistent benefits in preventing fractures than either nutrient alone. Clinical trials have demonstrated that combined supplementation can reduce the risk of hip and non-vertebral fractures significantly. Combined supplementation with 1200 mg of calcium per day and 800 IU of vitamin D per day has been recommended for prevention of fractures in older adults having low vitamin D level and living in institutions [5, 9, 10, 11]. Furthermore, meta-analyses indicate that higher compliance with supplementation correlates with a greater reduction in fracture risk, suggesting that both nutrients are essential for effective osteoporosis prevention strategies [7].

To summarize, adequate intake of calcium and vitamin D is critical for maintaining bone health and preventing postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis. Their synergistic effects enhance bone density and reduce fracture risk, particularly in older populations. Healthcare providers should emphasize the importance of these nutrients in

dietary recommendations and consider supplementation strategies to ensure optimal bone health in aging individuals.

However, some of the studies do not support the routine use of calcium and vitamin D either alone or in combination to lower the risk of fractures in elderly population [12, 13, 14 15]. So, the present systematic review was conducted to investigate the role of vitamin D and calcium for prevention of postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis.

Method

This systematic review was conducted following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guideline [16].

A comprehensive literature search was conducted across multiple databases, including PubMed, Science Direct and Cochrane Library to identify randomized controlled trials (RCTs) published from 2014 to 2024. The search terms included "calcium", "vitamin D", "postmenopausal osteoporosis", "senile osteoporosis" and "fracture". Studies were included if they assessed the effects of calcium and/or vitamin D supplementation on postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis in older adults.

We included only original research studies like randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and clinical trials conducted on older adults ≥ 50 years and published in English language. Exclusion criteria included studies that didn't evaluate any of the interventions of vitamin D or calcium in the management of postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis. We excluded reviews, meta-analyses, case studies, commentaries, editorials and short communications. Studies having only abstract and non-access of full text were also excluded. Studies done on animals were excluded.

A pre-screening or pilot literature review was meticulously conducted to ensure the reliability and credibility of the literature selection process. This pre-screening was performed by two independent researchers, and discrepancies were settled by a third reviewer. Title and abstract of each study were thoroughly examined to ascertain its relevance to the research objectives.

Data extraction and synthesis was performed after appropriate screening of the studies based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The extracted data included publication year, country, sample size, design of the study, mean age of the participants, interventions, and main findings of the study. The collected data were presented as findings of this systematic review after analysis.

Result

Initial search identified 1276 studies from the databases and other sources. 1003 records were screened after initial exclusion of the studies. Following an assessment of the titles and abstracts, 32 articles were selected for further consideration. Following that, 10 studies were eliminated based

on the inclusion criteria and three studies were not in English. We screened 19 studies based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Finally, we selected 12 studies because of non-availability of some data in the other studies. The process of selection of the studies is depicted in the PRISMA study selection diagram (Figure 1).

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Chart

Table 1: Comparison of different methods used for male circumcision

Authors & Publication Year	Country	Sample Size/ Design of the Study	Mean Age (Years)	Intervention	Findings
Chen Y et al. 2016[17]	China	210 RCT	56.4	Milk powder supplementation with different calcium contents (300, 600, and 900 mg per day for groups A, B, and C, respectively) and all groups received 800 IU of vitamin D per day.	Calcium supplementation at doses of 600 mg and 900 mg per day effectively reduced bone loss in the lumbar spine and greater trochanter, while 300 mg/day was ineffective.
Mason C et al. 2016[18]	United States	218 postmenopausal women; RCT	59.6	Oral vitamin D3 supplementation (cholecalciferol, 2000 IU/day) vs. placebo combined with weight loss intervention and aerobic exercise.	Vitamin D3 supplementation (2000 IU/day) during weight loss led to a decrease in leg strength without affecting lean mass or bone mineral density.

Pop LC et al. 2017[19]	United States	81 postmenopausal women; RCT	58	Multivitamin/ Mineral, Calcium and Vitamin D. Vitamin D3 supplementation (600, 2000, 4000 IU) with 1.2 g Ca/day	Higher vitamin D ₃ supplementation prevents decline in cortical thickness of the tibia.
Rahme M et al. 2017[15]	Lebanon and United States	257 elderly male and female; RCT	71	1000 mg of elemental calcium citrate/day, and the daily equivalent of 3,750IU/day or 600 IU/day of vitamin D3 for one year.	3,750 IU of vitamin D daily did not improve bone markers or density compared to the recommended 600 IU.
Tanakol R et al. 2018 [20]	Turkey	120 women; Controlled clinical trial	50	Group 1 received 1000 IU of cholecalciferol and 1 g of calcium daily. Group 2 received 0.5 µg calcitriol in addition to 400 IU of cholecalciferol and 1 g of calcium daily.	Calcitriol supplementation significantly increased lumbar spine BMD in patients with low vitamin D levels.
Reyes-Garcia R et al. 2018 [21]	Spain	500 healthy postmenopausal women; RCT	59	Low dose group subjects received semi-skimmed milk (calcium 120 mg/ 100 mL and vitamin D 30 IU/ 100 mL). Vitamin D group received semi-skimmed milk enriched with calcium (180 mg/100 mL) and vitamin D (120 IU/100 mL). Vitamin D + FOS group received semi-skimmed milk enriched with calcium (180 mg/100 mL), vitamin D (120 IU/100 mL), and FOS (5 g/L).	Calcium and vitamin D-enriched milk improved vitamin D status and BMD at the femoral neck.
Kruger MC et al. 2018 [22]	Malaysia	121 women; RCT	59.5	Control group received regular milk, 428 mg calcium per day) and intervention group received fortified milk at 1200 mg calcium, 96 mg magnesium, 2.4 mg zinc, 15 µg vitamin D and 4 g FOS-inulin per day).	Fortified milk with extra calcium and vitamin D tends to increase femoral neck bone mineral density (BMD).
Burt LA et al. 2019[14]	Canada	311 healthy adults; RCT	61.9	Daily doses of vitamin D ₃ for 3 years at 400 IU (n=109), 4000 IU (n=100), or 10000 IU (n=102). Calcium supplementation was provided to participants with dietary intake of less than 1200 mg per day.	High-dose vitamin D (4000 IU and 10,000 IU) resulted in lower BMD at some sites, questioning the benefits of high doses.
Zhou J et al. 2020 [23]	China	123 patients; RCT	83.54	Experiment group received 600 mg/d of calcium carbonate, 0.5 µg/d of alfacalcidol, and 70 mg/week of alendronate, while patients in the control group received 600 mg/d of calcium carbonate and 0.5 µg/d of alfacalcidol for 18 months.	The combination of alendronate, alfacalcidol, and calcium improved lumbar spine and femoral neck BMD.
Morato-	Spain	79 women; RCT	56	Experimental group re-	Increased calcium and

Martínez M et al. 2020 [24]				ceived 501 mg calcium and 6 µg vitamin D3 while control group received 227 mg calcium and 0.015 µg vitamin D3. Other supplements were also provided to both the groups.	vitamin D maintained or increased BMD compared to controls.
Iuliano S et al. 2021[25]	Australia	7195 elderly; RCT	86	Intervention facility received total intake of 1142 (353) mg calcium/day and 69 (15) g/day protein (1.1 g/kg body weight). Control facility consumed 700 (247) mg/day calcium and 58 (14) g/day protein (0.9 g/kg body weight).	Improved dietary calcium and protein intake from dairy reduced fall and fracture risks in aged care residents.
Feng F et al. 2021[26]	China	420 patients; RCT	70	NA VitD group took 800 mg calcium and 800 IU non-active vitamin D. P-NA VitD group took 800 mg calcium, 800 IU non-active vitamin D, and received physical exercise. A VitD group took 800 mg calcium and 0.5 µg active vitamin D. P-A VitD took 800 mg calcium, 0.5 µg active vitamin D, and received physical exercise.	Active vitamin D improved muscle strength and functional ability in elderly patients, reducing fall risks.

Table 1 summarizes the results of various studies focusing on calcium and vitamin D supplementation and their effects on bone health among different populations. The findings of the current systematic review included multiple studies published between 2016 and 2021.

The studies are conducted across several countries, including China, the United States, Lebanon, Turkey, Spain, Malaysia, Canada, and Australia. This international scope enhances the generalizability of the findings, indicating that the research on supplementation and bone health transcends cultural and dietary differences. This geographical diversity reflects a global interest in understanding the role of calcium and vitamin D in bone health, especially in older and at-risk populations.

Sample sizes ranged from 79 to 7195, indicating both large population studies and smaller focused trials. The majority of the studies are Randomized Controlled Trials (RCT), which are considered the gold standard in clinical research because they minimize bias and allow for causal inferences. Only one study is noted as controlled clinical trials (Tanakol R et al. 2018).[20] Participants' ages range from approximately 50 to 86 years old, indicating a focus on older adults and women at high risk for osteoporosis and bone health issues: younger participants of 50 years (Tanakol R et al.)

[20] and older participants of 86 years (Iuliano S et al.) [25] The interventions varied significantly across studies, involving different dosages of calcium and vitamin D: calcium dosages ranged from 300 mg to 1200 mg per day and Vitamin D dosages varied from 400 IU to 10,000 IU per day, with multiple forms (e.g., cholecalciferol). Two studies included exercises or dietary changes as part of the interventions, indicating a multifaceted approach to improving bone health.

The studies generally suggest that adequate dosages of calcium and vitamin D, either alone or in combination with other factors like exercise and nutrition, can have significant benefits for bone health, particularly in vulnerable populations like postmenopausal women and the elderly. While many studies reported positive outcomes, others, particularly those examining high-dose vitamin D, raised questions about the efficacy and safety of large amounts of supplementation without observed benefits in bone health markers.

Discussion

The aim of our systematic review is to investigate the role of vitamin D and calcium for prevention of postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis. The findings of the current study provide a comprehensive overview of various studies examining the effects of calcium and vitamin D supplementation on bone

health, particularly in specific populations such as postmenopausal women and the elderly.

The included studies demonstrate that calcium and vitamin D are crucial for maintaining bone health, especially in vulnerable populations like postmenopausal women and the elderly. While the benefits of supplementation are well-supported, the studies also raise important questions about optimal dosages, long-term effects, and the need for individualized approaches based on specific health needs. Calcium supplementation is utilized in the studies of Chen et al. (2016) [17] and Zhou et al. (2020) [23]. Chen et al. (2016) [17] found that calcium supplementation of 600 mg/day significantly reduced bone loss in the lumbar spine and greater trochanter among postmenopausal women, with 900 mg/day being more effective for the greater trochanter. This study confirmed high calcium milk powder supplementation is beneficial for the prevention of bone loss in elderly women, which is consistent with several previous reports [27,28,29,30].

The study is not consistent with the findings of Bolland et al. (2015) [31] who suggested that calcium supplementation alone does not have a protective effect on bone fractures in older adults, raising questions about the adequacy of supplementation without other forms of intervention. Zhou et al. (2020) [23] reported that a combination of alendronate sodium, alfacalcidol, and calcium significantly improved bone mineral density (BMD) at the lumbar spine and femoral neck.

Vitamin D Supplementation is reported by Pop et al. (2017) [19] and Rahme et al. (2017) [15]. Pop et al. (2017) [19] indicated that higher doses of vitamin D3 (up to 4000 IU) helped prevent declines in cortical thickness of the tibia, suggesting a protective role against bone density loss. Similar findings are also reported by Sahni et al. (2016) [32] who found that vitamin D status was positively correlated with bone density measurements in older adults, suggesting that adequate vitamin D levels are essential for maintaining bone structure. Rahme et al. (2017) [15], however, found that a high dose of vitamin D (3750 IU) did not improve BMD compared to the standard RDA of 600 IU, indicating that excessive vitamin D might not confer additional benefits in certain populations. Combined supplementation of calcium and vitamin D is used by Reyes-Garcia et al. (2018) [21] and Burt et al. (2019) [14]. Reyes-Garcia et al. (2018) [21] demonstrated that milk enriched with calcium and vitamin D significantly improved BMD at the femoral neck and had positive effects on metabolic profiles in postmenopausal women. Burt et al. (2019) [14] noted that high doses of vitamin D (4000 IU and 10000 IU) were associated with lower BMD at the

radius and tibia, raising concerns about the efficacy of high-dose vitamin D supplementation.

These studies are consistent with the findings of Heaney (2009) [33] who indicated that dairy products could be valuable dietary sources of calcium and vitamin D, contributing to improved bone health. However, there are contradictory findings that have been reported by several studies. Some studies showed that calcium supplementation combined with vitamin D reduced the risk of fractures [26, 20,15] while others showed no effect [34, 35, 19, 36, 37]. In the current study, supplementation is also used in combination with exercise by Feng et al. (2021) [26] who found that active vitamin D combined with physical exercise improved muscle strength and reduced fall risk in elderly patients with osteoporosis, highlighting the importance of physical activity alongside supplementation.

A meta-analysis by Tang et al. (2007) [38] supports the notion that calcium and vitamin D supplementation can reduce fracture risk, particularly in populations with high compliance to supplementation regimens. This aligns with the findings of Chen et al. (2016) and Reyes-Garcia et al. (2018) regarding the benefits of adequate calcium and vitamin D intake. Combined interventions are applied by some of the studies. Tanakol R et al. (2018) [20] demonstrated that calcitriol (active vitamin D) combined with calcium significantly increased lumbar spine BMD in patients with osteoporosis. This supports the idea that active forms of vitamin D may be more effective than standard supplementation. Feng F et al. (2021) [26] emphasized the importance of combining active vitamin D with calcium and physical exercise, showing improvements in muscle strength and BMD, which can reduce fall risk in the elderly. This suggests that multifaceted approaches may yield better outcomes for bone health.

Dietary sources and fortification are used in some of the research. Reyes-Garcia R et al. (2018) [21] and Kruger MC et al. (2018) [22] found that dietary sources of calcium and vitamin D, such as fortified milk, significantly improved BMD in postmenopausal women. This indicates that dietary interventions can be effective in enhancing bone health. Iuliano S et al. (2021) [25] further supports this by showing that increasing calcium and protein intake through dairy products can reduce fall and fracture risks in elderly care residents, emphasizing the role of nutrition in maintaining bone health.

In our systematic review, we found some contradictory studies that are inconsistent with the use of vitamin D in bone health. The findings of Burt et al. (2019) [14] contradict the general consensus on high-dose vitamin D, suggesting that

it may not provide additional benefits for bone health and could potentially lead to adverse effects. This is in contrast to studies that advocate for higher doses based on specific patient needs. Rahme et al. (2017) [15] also present a contradictory view by demonstrating that high doses of vitamin D did not improve bone health markers compared to standard doses, challenging the efficacy of high-dose supplementation strategies. The studies present a mixed response regarding the effectiveness of vitamin D supplementation alone, particularly at higher doses. While some studies advocate for higher doses, others warn against potential adverse effects and lack of benefits for bone density. The role of calcium is generally supported across studies, but its effectiveness can be influenced by the presence of other factors, such as vitamin D levels and overall dietary intake. The combination of calcium and active vitamin D appears to be more beneficial than either alone, particularly in populations at high risk for osteoporosis. Vitamin D supplementation has been considered effective for prevention and treatment of osteoporosis. However, recent meta-analyses do not support a major treatment benefit of vitamin D for osteoporosis [39, 40] or preventing falls [40] or fractures. [40,41]

Implications for Practice

Recommendations: There is a strong implication for healthcare providers to customize supplementation regimens based on individual needs, risk factors, and potential side effects. Further research is encouraged to clarify optimal dosages and combinations for bone health in diverse populations.

The conflicting evidence calls for more comprehensive and diverse clinical trials that not only test different dosages and combinations of calcium and vitamin D but also examine long-term outcomes on bone health, fall risk, and quality of life in various populations. Future research must consider the interplay of dietary sources, supplementation, lifestyle factors, and individual patient characteristics to formulate effective strategies for osteoporosis prevention and management.

Conclusion

The evidence surrounding calcium and vitamin D supplementation is nuanced, with both supporting and contradictory studies highlighting the need for individualized approaches based on patient demographics, existing health conditions, and compliance levels. While many studies advocate for the benefits of these nutrients in improving bone health, particularly in postmenopausal women and the elderly, others caution against high doses and emphasize the importance of adherence to supplementation regimens for optimal outcomes.

The combination of calcium and active vitamin D appears to be more beneficial than either alone, particularly in populations at high risk for osteoporosis. It is concluded that calcium and vitamin D supplementation plays a vital role in preventing postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis and reducing fracture risk in older adults.

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